

Comparison of Measuring Systems for Puncture Test According to IEC 61211

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Abstract: In this paper, we summarise the experience gained during comparisons between four measuring systems designed specifically for performing the test according to IEC 61211. Two of the systems are based on dividers using low-ohmic wire-wound resistors. The other two are identical and they are based on dividers using ceramic resistors both in high-voltage and low-voltage arms. Two comparisons were performed by measuring the flashover voltage on a glass insulator simultaneously with two or three systems. A 120 kV insulator was tested in both cases, and the test voltage was approximately 270 kV. Both the recorded waveforms and measured peak values were compared, even though only the peak value measurement is required by the present standard. The first comparison was performed between one ceramic and one wire-wound divider. The second comparison performed in a different laboratory was between two ceramic and the other wire-wound dividers. Even with the compact test circuits used, and with wideband measuring systems specifically built for this test, large differences in the waveforms measured with different systems were observed. In most cases the agreement in measured peak values was within 3 %. Higher differences occurred only in one measuring circuit setup on negative polarity with one divider in an abnormal measurement position.

1. INTRODUCTION

In service, line insulators are stressed by lightning overvoltages. The amplitude and the steepness of the actual stress are influenced by both the rated line voltage and number of insulator discs in the insulator string. The present version of the puncture testing standard is based on the work performed in CIGRE Task Force 33.07.01 in late 80's [1]. The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) describes methods and requirement for puncture test on ceramic and glass insulators in standard IEC 61211 [2].

IEC 61211 proposes in its informative annex some requirements for the measuring system used in the puncture test. The overall uncertainty of the measuring system should be no more than 5 %, and the uncertainty of the divider scale factor should be less than 2 %. However, the accuracy of this measuring system is difficult to assess, as there is no calibration services readily available. In addition, the requirements for the test setup details are not very well defined in the standard, e.g., the grounding arrangement, size of the divider, and inductance of the measurement loop all have a significant effect on measurement result.

For puncture tests on insulators in accordance with IEC 61211, fast-rise impulses are applied with a reported rise-time of 200 ns at voltages reaching 500 kV. The aim of the test is to ensure that, even for very fast transient overvoltage, there is a flashover along the insulator surface, instead of

puncture through the glass or ceramic insulator. The test is performed by increasing the steepness of the test impulse until specified test voltage is obtained across the insulator under test. The required test voltage is typically between 2.0 to 2.8 times the lightning impulse 50 % flashover voltage.

Comparisons between tests and field experience have pointed out that impulse voltage puncture tests on insulators units are effective in reducing the risk of failure in service, revealing potential design problems or fabrication defects. In an impulse puncture test, a fast rising voltage is applied to the disk insulator. This should not lead to puncture of the solid insulation, but to an external flashover.

It is usually difficult for a system designed for lightning impulse (LI) testing to fulfil the requirements of measuring such fast impulses. The main practical difficulty with the LI divider is its large size (height), which prevents building a compact test setup.

A compact setup for puncture testing has been proposed in literature [3][4]. The paper presents a solution where the sphere gap, divider and insulator holder have all been collected into one movable setup. Proper grounding practices have also been introduced.

This paper summarises the experience gained during comparisons between four measuring and Fortum, are identical, and they are based on ceramic resistors for both high-voltage and systems designed specifically for performing the test

according to IEC 61211. As far as we know, this is the first interlaboratory comparison published related with measurement of IEC 61211 waveforms. Two of the systems, VTT MIKES low-voltage arms of the divider. The other two, CEPEL and NMI-Australia (NMIA) systems, are based on dividers using low-ohmic wire-wound resistors. Aspects related to the different systems and different setups used in the comparisons are discussed.

2. MEASURING SYSTEMS

2.1. VTT MIKES system

The VTT MIKES system is based on ceramic resistors, and a general schematic diagram for a resistive divider is shown in Figure 1. The high voltage arm R1 consists of a stack of 26 units of 200 Ω ceramic disk resistors, and the low voltage arm R2 is a single 5 Ω ceramic disk resistors housed in a cylindrical brass. The 45 Ω resistor R3 matches the output to the 50 Ω coaxial cable T1, which feeds the signal to a wideband (3 GHz) pulse attenuator (R4 to R6) with 34 dB attenuation. The nominal voltage attenuation ratio of the system is c. 82000:1 when connected to 50 Ω input (R7) of a wideband oscilloscope [5]. A 15 meter coaxial cable with 100 % shield coverage was used. In this work an oscilloscope with 500 MHz bandwidth and 1 GS/s sampling rate was used. Impulse parameters were calculated from the measured data without additional filtering.

Figure 1: General schematic diagram of puncture test divider system.

2.2. Fortum system

The Fortum system was based on similar ceramic divider design. It consists of a custom attenuator [6] and a digitizer with 150 MHz bandwidth and 200 MS/s sample rate. Impulse parameters were calculated from the measured data without additional filtering.

2.3. CEPEL system

The CEPEL system is based on very low-ohmic wire-wound and hand-made resistors, following the same general schematic diagram for a resistive divider shown in Figure 1, with R3 and R6 not being present in the CEPEL system. The nominal resistance values are $R1 = 2100 \Omega$, $R2 = R4 = 3 \Omega$, $R5 = 47 \Omega$ and $R7 = 50 \Omega$.

The scale factor calculated from measured resistance values is 13258:1. The digitizer used is an 8-bit oscilloscope with 1 GHz bandwidth and 1.25 GS/s sampling rate. It is connected to the divider via a 7.5 meter long double shielded coaxial cable with 50 Ω characteristic impedance. Impulse parameters are determined after filtering the measured raw data with a wavelet-based digital filter [7].

The scale factor of the CEPEL system was also determined by comparison with the VTT MIKES reference LI measurement system [8][9]. Both systems measured simultaneously voltage impulses of 40 kV peak, with front time of 0.5 μs and time-to-half value of 30 μs . The scale factor resulted from this impulse comparison measurement was 13492:1, which differs almost 2 % from the calculated scale factor. The reason for this difference is probably the resistances of the central conductor and shield of the coaxial cable, which were not taken into account when calculating the scale factor from resistance values.

CEPEL divider was designed, constructed and characterized for use in vertical position.

2.4. NMI-Australia system

The high-voltage divider of the NMIA system consists of a 3.3 k Ω high-voltage arm resistor, a 10 Ω low-voltage arm resistor and a 42 Ω matching resistor that was connected in series with the inner conductor of the measurement cable. The 50 Ω coaxial cable used has 100 % shield coverage to reduce interference pick-up, and it feeds the signal to a wideband (3 GHz) pulse attenuator with 34 dB attenuation. The attenuator was terminated with a 50 Ω terminator and was connected to 1 M Ω input of the digitizer. NMIA system uses an 8-bit digitizer with 500 MHz bandwidth and 1 GS/s sampling rate.

3. STEP RESPONSE MEASUREMENTS

Step response measurements were performed using two different step voltage generators and digital recorders. In general, the step response of each measurement system was sensitive even to small changes in the setup in the high voltage hall and grounding arrangements of the digital recorder.

Figure 2 shows the step response of the VTT divider with the attenuator, measured using the 500 MHz 1GS/s digitizer. VTT step generator is based on a mercury-wetted relay and it creates a falling voltage step with fixed output of approximately 300 V.

The step response of the CEPEL system is shown in Figure 3. CEPEL step generator was also based on mercury-wetted relay with fixed output voltage

Figure 2: VTT system step response with attenuator. Step voltage at digitizer input was approximately 3.5 mV.

Figure 3: CEPEL system step response without attenuator. Step voltage at digitizer input was approximately 8 mV.

Figure 4: NMIA system step response.

of approximately 90 V. The measurements were performed using 1 GHz, 5 GS/s digitizer. Records were taken without the attenuator in order to obtain a high enough voltage level for the oscilloscope.

The step response of the NMIA system is shown in Figure 4.

4. MEASUREMENT SETUPS

Three different setups were used during the comparisons. The setups were made as compact as possible. The principle of the puncture test setup is shown in Figure 5. A steeping gap is used in the output of a lightning impulse voltage generator and the voltage is measured across the terminals of the insulator under test. The steeping gap was close to the test object and the high voltage leads of the dividers were kept short.

In each setup special care was taken to ensure low inductance grounding both from the impulse generator to the insulator under test and from the insulator under test to each divider.

Figure 5: Circuit for test voltage generation and measurement.

4.1. Setup 1

The first setup shown in Figure 6 was arranged in the high voltage laboratory of NMIA. The comparison was performed between NMIA and VTT dividers. In this setup different charging voltages were used and, consequently, the peak voltage and time to flashover were varied. A sample of the measured waveforms for the higher charging and peak voltage are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Setup 1. NMIA divider on the left (red), VTT divider (green) in the front.

Lower charging voltage leads to lower peak value and wider impulse, as shown in the samples of Figure 8. The signals from the two dividers were measured using two channels of the NMIA digitizer. An 11-point moving average filter was used on both channels for waveform smoothing.

Figure 7: Positive impulse with 100 ns rise time measured by the two dividers of setup 1 shown in Figure 6. The puncture impulse waveforms are shifted in time for displaying purpose in all related figures in this paper.

Figure 8: Positive impulse with 160 ns rise time measured by the two dividers of setup 1 shown in Figure 6.

4.2. Setups 2 and 3

The second and third setups were arranged in the high voltage laboratory of Fortum in Finland. Another type of insulator was used, and in this setup the time to voltage collapse was approximately 200 ns. The comparison was performed between three measuring systems from VTT, CEPEL and Fortum, each composed of a divider, signal transmission cable, attenuator(s), digital recorder and software for parameter evaluation.

Before the puncture test measurements, scale factors of all systems were calibrated against a lightning impulse reference system at 45 kV.

In setup 2 shown in Figure 9, the CEPEL divider was in the vertical position, as it was originally characterized and mandatorily used in tests. Typical impulses measured in setup are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

The only difference of setup 3 shown in Figure 12 from setup 2 is that now the CEPEL divider is also in the diagonal position. The aim of this change is to study the influence of inductive loop present in setup 2. The loop was formed by the high voltage input lead, the divider and ground return. Increased

stray capacitances due to the proximity of the top electrode of CEPEL divider to ground may also influence. Influence of proximity effect of CEPEL divider in this position on the other two dividers is also possible. Typical impulses measured in setup 3 are shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 9: Setup 2. CEPEL divider on the left (white), VTT divider (green) in the front and Fortum divider on the right. The impulse generator feeding the steeping gap inside the insulator housing (brown shed porcelain) is in the background.

Figure 10: Positive impulses measured in setup 2 shown in Figure 9.

Figure 11: Negative impulses measured in setup 2 shown in Figure 9.

Figure 12: Setup 3. Like setup 2, but CEPEL divider (white) is now in diagonal position.

Figure 13: Positive impulses measured in setup 2 shown in Figure 12.

Figure 14: Negative impulses measured in setup 3 shown in Figure 12.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Different systems

Results recorded with VTT divider (setup 1) or VTT system (setups 2 and 3) were selected as reference for presentation of the results in this paper. However, VTT results should not be considered more accurate than those from NMIA, CEPEL or Fortum.

The impulses were measured simultaneously with all systems connected to the test object. The difference ΔU_p from the reference was calculated for each impulse by formula

$$\Delta U_p = \frac{U_m - U_{ref}}{U_{ref}} \cdot 100\%,$$

where U_{ref} is the peak value measured by the VTT system, and U_m that measured by one of the other systems. The average and standard deviation of 10 impulses was calculated for each case, even though the impulse waveform and amplitude varied.

The results of comparison performed at NMIA in setup 1 for the two dividers are shown in Figure 15 and Table 1. In this case the 95 % uncertainty of the comparison was also evaluated.

Figure 15: Comparison between NMIA and VTT dividers for different rise times and polarities in setup 1. Error bars show the estimated uncertainty of comparison.

Table 1: Comparison results at NMIA – Differences of NMIA system with the VTT divider as the reference

Waveshape		U_p [kV]	NMIA	
			ΔU_p	Unc. ($k=2$)
Steep	pos	337	1.5%	1.2%
	neg	-344	1.4%	1.2%
Moderate	pos	311	0.4%	1.2%
	neg	-311	-0.2%	1.2%

The differences and experimental standard deviations of the comparison performed between CEPEL, Fortum and VTT systems in setups 2 and 3 are shown in Table 2 and Figure 16. There is no significant difference between the comparison results for positive voltage. However, for negative voltage the setup change influenced also the difference between the two dividers that were not moved.

Table 2: Comparison results at Fortum – Differences from VTT system reading together with experimental standard deviations.

Setup		U_p [kV]	CEPEL		FORTUM	
			ΔU_p	s	ΔU_p	s
Setup2, Vertical	pos	263	-0.4%	2.0%	-2.1%	1.5%
	neg	-272	0.2%	0.7%	2.5%	2.1%
Setup 3, Diagonal	pos	273	-1.8%	0.6%	-0.1%	2.8%
	neg	-274	-6.7%	2.3%	-5.8%	2.6%

Figure 16: Comparison between CEPEL, Fortum and VTT systems in setups 2 and 3. Error bars show one standard deviation of comparison results.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Different wideband measuring systems specifically designed for puncture testing were compared. In most cases the agreement in peak values is within 3 %. Higher differences occurred only in negative polarity in one measuring circuit setup, where one divider was used in abnormal position.

The results show that the requirement of 5 % overall uncertainty ($k=2$) set in IEC 61211 for puncture test voltage measurement may be achieved, when the measuring systems are specifically designed and the test circuits are carefully arranged for measurement of fast phenomena.

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